

Water and carbon footprint for two condensing configurations for a solar thermal power plant

SolarPACES 2024

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1. Introduction

Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) technology works by directing solar rays onto a receiver through mirrors, lenses, and optical devices to generate heat. This heat is then transferred to a Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF) and employed to drive a thermodynamic cycle, typically a Rankine cycle, for producing electricity. In Rankine power plants, the steam existing the turbine is condensed for reuse in the steam generator. This condensation process can occur through a wet, dry, or a hybrid configuration [1]. Wet cooling is often preferred because the superior thermal properties of water excel over those of air. Currently, there are 114 operational CSP plants, where more than 85% of them use some sort of wet cooling system [2]. The issue of water scarcity is exacerbating as floods and droughts intensify, and precipitation patterns shift due to climate change. Consequently, this could result in environmental restrictions on water consumption, forcing to reduce the water usage of CSP plants [1]. The aim of this study is to assess the water and carbon footprint of two alternative condensing system configurations, wet and hybrid, of a central tower CSP plant located in Sevilla (Spain), by means of the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology. Considering the optimal thermo-economic performance of both configurations, the water and carbon footprint is calculated as CO₂ emissions and cubic meters of water consumed by each system per year. The dry condensing system consists of several induced-draft air-cooled condenser cells (ACCs) and the hybrid system consists of a parallel system where the condensing steam is split between the ACCs and a surface steam condenser where circulating water is cooled in a wet mechanical-draft cooling tower (WT). [1]

2. Methodology

The steps of the standardized LCA methodology [3] are as follows: i. goal and scope definition, ii. life cycle inventory, iii. impact assessment and iv. interpretation. (i) The goal and scope of the present work is to assess the environmental performance of two alternative condensing technologies for a central tower CSP. For this purpose, Table 1 (ii) lists the constituent materials, water, and electricity consumption of both configurations. The CSP plant analyzed is located in Sevilla, with a central tower molten salt receiver configuration, 10 hours of thermal energy storage, a lifetime of 30 years, and a capacity factor of 0.7 [2]. The typical meteorological year (TMY) was chosen to represent climate conditions in 2020. The functional unit is 1 year of operation.

The optimal equipment for both configurations is 24 ACC (dry) and 16 ACC and 3 WT (hybrid). Both configurations have been chosen following the results proposed by Marugán-Cruz et al. [1]. The European Commission's Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) 3.0 method [4] was used to analyze the potential environmental impacts of the condensing configurations. The selected impact categories were climate change and water use. The calculations (iii) were conducted using the SimaPro 9.5 software and Ecoinvent 3.9 database.

Table 1. Dry and Hybrid condensing systems configurations Life Cycle Inventory for year 2020 [5].

Condensing system		Inputs	Amount	Units
Dry	Materials	Steel	67.8	Ton
		Concrete		
	Power	ACC fan	27190	W
		ACC pump	34478	W
Water consumption	Water	0	m ³	
Hybrid	Materials	Steel	207.5	Ton
		Concrete	992.43	Ton
	Power	ACC fan	25092	W
		ACC pump	32183	W
		WT fan	39152	W
		Surface steam condenser pump	56480	W
	Water consumption	Water	4.64E+05	m ³

3. Results

Fig. 1: Dry and Hybrid configuration results for a) climate change [kgCO_{2eq}] and b) water use [m³] impacts for 2020.

Fig. 1 shows the environmental results for the systems analyzed for a) climate change and b) water use impact categories. Regarding climate change, dry configuration shows the worst carbon footprint. A reduction of 22% in kg CO_{2eq} emissions is observed when the hybrid system is utilized. In both, electricity consumption is the major contributor to climate change. Water footprint is significantly larger in the hybrid system than the dry system, demonstrating a reduction of 92% in water use when the dry system is utilized.

4. Conclusions

This study concludes that while the hybrid system exhibits a better environmental profile concerning climate change, conversely, the dry system demonstrates a significant advantage in water consumption. An interesting finding is that steel and concrete, the materials that constitute the condensing equipment, have not been found to have a significant percentage of environmental damage contribution.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the EU-funded HORIZON MSCA "TOPCSP" Doctoral Network Project: [grant number 101072537].

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